

About the teaching of the Theory and History of Modern Architecture and Urbanism: for the dissemination of new notions and concepts

*"The principles in philosophy are cries around
which concepts develop real short stories"*
Deleuze/Guattari

Introduction

In the 60s, the balance of the exhaustive cultural debate between those who made statements on cultural paradigmatic changes in the sense of showing ruptures, and the ones who presupposed it was part of the dynamics and continuity of the incomplete process of modernity, was a set of new presuppositions, notions and concepts especially incorporated in the repertoire of discourse in different areas of knowledge, and in the disciplines of the theory and history of architecture and urbanism, even though in an incipient way.

In the specific case of modern architecture produced in Brazil and especially in terms of urbanistic experiences, there was a proliferation of recent theoretical studies, especially the historical ones. However, most of them did not incorporate the emerging discourse transformations into the present cultural context, although the discourse production of the texts written by Lucio Costa, Paulo Santos, Yves Bruan, Carlos Lemos, Mario Barata, among others (Puppi, 1998:) was criticized.

The present text proposes to contribute in some way to the rereading of modern architecture produced in Brazil, based on some notions and con-

cepts of the new discipline discourse, with the objective of disseminating a new discourse repertoire, implementing new notions and concepts.

For this purpose, the "formation of discourse" concept developed by Foucault was used as a starting point. It was transposed to the disciplinary area of architecture and urbanism, and in this case to the discourse about theory and history of the "modern movement" and modern architecture and urbanism. The notions and/or concepts of space and time inherited from modernity are being questioned today, owing to the advent of technological/space/time and consequently to their limited applicability when compared to the leading edge technology and presuppositions that at the beginning were questioned by the quantum physics under the protection of the indetermination principle. Some initial considerations were made in terms of new notions, concepts, pairs of concepts and several experiences, bearing in mind their repercussion in the architecture discourse. Heterotopia, rhizome, deconstruction, hyperspace, time/space/technology, amongst others were selected as examples, used only as references not to lengthen the text.

In the new cultural/technological context, having in mind the inexhaustible informational file and envisaging Internet and other communications modalities, it is expected that the recycled "virtual communities and the academia" undertake the responsibility for establishing a new "modern movement" discourse.

Formation of discourse

There seems to be a consensus regarding the galloping advent of the New World economy, configured in the globalization process, under the protection of a new way of "flexible capital" production. Consonant with this project, a new formation of discourse arises, not only in the strictly economic sense but also affecting the cultural context. The referred event is characterized by the emergence of a new set of notions and concepts with higher visibility in the epistemological and technological universe.

The formation of discourse concept adopted here refers to Foucault's seminal text "The Archaeology of Knowledge". The author begins with a series of hypothesis based on an enunciation different in form and disperse in time, and which refer to the same and sole object, analyzing types of chain of thoughts, identity and persistence, having in mind the establishment of a new strategic possibility.

For example, taking architecture and urbanism into consideration, which set of enunciation emanates from our practices, using notions and concepts to organize discourse in our area of knowledge? Paraphrasing Foucault, we would ask: where

can we base the identification of the object on which we will develop a discourse? We will certainly face a series of lacunas and entangling of events, games of differences, offsets, substitutions and transformations, formulations of highly different levels and too heterogeneous functions. In reality we are:

“in the presence of concepts that are different in terms of structure and utilization rules, ignoring or excluding each other and unable to enter the unit of a logic architecture.... In the case described above, we would by convection say that this is the “formation of discourse” amidst a series of enunciations, such a dispersion system, in which the objects, the kinds of enunciations, the concepts, the themes, can define a regularity (an order, correlation, positions and functionality, transformations. (Foucault, 1987: 42-43). In this quotation, according to our perception, Foucault’s reference to a “new order” must be interpreted as a new order that will have a connotation, concern, nonsense of chaotic disturbance for those who resist to maintain the formation of discourse, archeologically based and opposing to changes.

It is worth reminding that at the same time the discourse for an integral architecture was being established in the Bauhaus scope, taking Gropius’ renowned text as an example, there was a conceptual revolution in physics, which would directly or indirectly affect the most diverse disciplinary fields: the indetermination principle (or principle of uncertainty). On one hand, the explanation of the paradigm of modernity in architecture and urbanism, clinging to the principle of pure rationality, the functional aspect of the design, the notion of unity, totality and insertion into a world of capitalism production, industry, namely a set of ideas impregnated with an ideology focusing on a social nature utopia. The CIAM discourses reinforced and expanded these presuppositions for the understanding of the cities, under the protection of the time/space equation originating from the concepts of Euclidean nature (the space) and the ones of classical mechanics (the chronological time).

On the other hand, the quantum physics and its enunciation affected the time/space relationship elaborated by modernity; a relationship that had already been highly affected by the Theory of Relativity. However, six decades later, the principle of indetermination obtained little repercussion on the applied social sciences, precisely in the case of architecture and urbanism. It is not an easy task to encourage the subversion of given notions such as unity, totality, order and mainly the notions inherited from space and time favoring, for example, the ones of pluralism, difference, chaos, heterotopia and technological/time/space. The author of the mentioned principle,

the physicist Werner Heisenberg, after being aware of the natural reactions to these new conceptions observed: “pluralism exerts no fascination on those who prefer to think about fundamental principals. But, after all, this is a reasonable commitment, for on one hand it avoids the difficulties of monism and on the other it enables the introduction of a given type of order”. (Heisenberg, 1995: 53). This notion of order is equivalent to the one Foucault mentioned some decades later, or in other words the conditions to which the objects, modality of enunciation, concept and thematic choices are submitted. Rules that express conditions of existence, but also of coexistence, maintenance, modification and also disappearance in a given moment of the formation of discourse, which must be understood as a non linear process and whose series of events present configurations with lacunas and uncertain, indeterminable, unpredictable sequences. Rules and conditions that are established amongst institutions, economic and social processes; ways of behavior, system of standards, techniques, types of classification, ways of characterization. (Foucault, 1987: 51). Basically these relationships define discourse as a “practice”. The discourses transmitted, especially in the academic media, should not be confused with a set of signs (signifying elements that indicate contents or representations), but as practices that form notions, concepts and objects they talk about in a systematic way, shaping the development of professions.

The Theory and History of Architecture and Urbanism

The historiography of architecture and urbanism is based on the notions of space and time. The text “Space, Time and Architecture”, written by Giedion and published in 1941 is one example of the Theory and History of modern architecture that had a huge repercussion in the formation of generations of architects. It was written at a time of political and cultural conflicts, and the author dedicated the text:

“to those concerned with the present conditions of our culture and anxious to find refuge in the apparent chaos of their contradictory trends. I tried to establish, both with arguments and data, a secret synthesis of our apparent civilization, despite this seemingly confusion and all the rest, an authentic, however, veiled unit (Giedion, 1954: IX). (Our emphasis).

Before Giedion, Platzer (1930), Pevsner (1936) and Behrent (1937) wrote about modern architecture. Later, Zevi (1951) and many other modern architecture and urbanism theorists and historians published essays that extended up to Frampton’s text

(1981) the "Critical History of the Modern Architecture" Therefore, half a century of theoretical and historiographical formulations, in which notions and concepts of space, time, shape, function, unit, integrity, continuity, homogeneity, balance, summary, order, organism, evolution, constructivism, among others, related to other notions and concepts, coming from economy and sociology (way of production, social classes etc), structured the new discourses of the architecture of the city.

With the advent of the new cultural era some authors decided to call post-modernity (or contemporaneity according to others), the theoretical and historiographical presuppositions of architecture and urbanism started to change. The emergence of a new set of notions started assuming a hegemonic position in several and diverse disciplinary discourses. Notions and concepts such as: plurality, complexity, difference, heterogeneity, heterotopia, discontinuity, transformation (instead of evolution), deconstruction, disjunction, rhizome, and technologic/space/time amongst others.

The arrival of the new technologies and the repercussion that these technologies had and have on architecture and urbanism contributed highly to the formation of the new conceptual repertoire. The loss of hegemony of the time/space equation in the theory and history of urban and architecture seems to be the most outstanding event in the new discourse level. The technologic/time/space concept (Virilio, 1995:) means the deconstruction of the Euclidean space, a process observed in some manifestations of the own modernity. According to Tafuri, Piranesi's spatial conceptions (18th century), expressing his architectonic proposals through illustrations, where the indefinite opening of spaces, one inside the other as well as their multiplication by several observation points, result in a kind of literal dismantling of the Euclidean space (Tafuri, 1980: 35). The text "Architettura in nuce" by Zevi stands out amidst the theory of architecture texts that document the crisis of the concept of space applied to the historiography of the city architecture, in a symptomatic way, in an attempt to redefine it. The concept of space was further reinterpreted by Norberg-Schulz, giving it an existential connotation (meaningful form experienced) at the same time trying to supersede both the Euclidean static conception and the dynamics formulated by Einstein. Thus, it was trying to establish a general theory of the architectonic symbolism, based on the "genius loci" notion, a theory of "place" in architecture, which will later find the "hyperspace" "anti-notion" in Jameson and the one of "no-place" in Augé.

As far as the Theory and History of the Architecture of the city are concerned, two authors, whose

trends still persist in the contemporaneous formation of discourse, formulated contemporaneously different architecture viewpoints: Roberto Venturi and Aldo Rossi. The former, inserted in the hegemonic universe of the American economic and cultural production, did not hesitate to announce that the advertisement, the publicity devices overlaid on the facades of the buildings were more important than architecture itself. (Venturi, 1977:). The latter, inserted in the heritage of the Italian historicism, searched the meaning of permanence as well as of the monuments in the message of the urban events, conceiving the city as architecture, history and collective memory. Despite the meaningful rupture with "modern architecture movement", each one in own way, one associating architecture with the universe of merchandise, the other renewing the ties with history and memory, both authors could not disassociate themselves from the Euclidean concept of physical space, incorporating to it contradictory and complex elements of existential and symbolic nature.

Similar to what happened to the Quantum Physics, in architecture the starting point of a new enunciation faces a paradox: any present architectonic and urbanistic experience has to be described using the Euclidean geometry repertoire, a language through which the arrangements and results are announced. Referring to the classic physics concepts (especially those of space and time) Heisenberg stated (1959):

"We cannot and we do not have the means to replace them for others". Despite that, the application of these concepts suffers limitations imposed by the indetermination principle. We must bear in mind the limited scope of applicability of these concepts, we cannot improve them, and thus we cannot try". (Heisenberg, 1995:39).

Today the question formulated by Heisenberg can be asked in a different way, thanks to the quick development of leading edge technology, which tests the concepts of space and time, up to that hegemonic point in the modernity discourse. The referred loss in the discursive domain does not necessarily mean the inapplicability of the concepts developed throughout the century, but their limitations, namely the limited discourse efficiency that they demonstrate. Concerning these limitations, relating architecture to state-of-the-art technologies, Virilio states a mortal sentence:

"Deprived of objective limitations, the architectonic element is drifting, floating on the electronic ether, without spatial dimensions, but inscribed in the sole temporality of an instantaneous diffusion.

From this point on, the built space participates in an electronic topology where the fitting of the stand point and the weave of the digital image renovate the notion of the urban sector... from now on urban architecture must relate to the opening of a technological time-space. Owing to the imperceptible material of the cathodic tube, the space dimensions became inseparable from its transmission speed " (Virilio, 1995: 9-11) (Our emphasis).

Discourse that means the instantaneousness of ubiquity, a form of atopia of the sole interface. This also means that the notion of physical dimension (distance, in space, and interval of time, is being abolished by the velocity of distance). The "primitive magnitude", inferior to all measurement, both of time and place becomes the speed of light. About this, Virilio said

" In reality, day and night ceased to organize life, from the moment that space and time lost their practical importance to give place to a major transparency, to a major cinemometric deepness, in which light all of a sudden acquires the status of raw material". (idem, 45).

We have thus witnessed a morphologic fracture that has been provoking an enormous ambiguity, carefully sustained between space and its shape, image, between time and its technical unrealization; real time (the instantaneity, the permanent present), a notion incorporated into the contemporaneous discourse.

Notions and emerging concepts – For a new formation of discourse

It seems contradictory to state that history is always a construction of the present, a radical and disturbing enunciation for those concerned with the theory and history of architecture, even though this statement must be here understood as the construction of discourse, in an attempt to relate some notions and emerging concepts, having in mind the rereading of the urban architecture production in the period of study; modern architecture and urbanism.

For example, it would seem contradictory to introduce the heterotopia concept (Foucault) in analytical and critical formulations related to the production of urban architecture during the period being mentioned, taking into account the vital principle of modern formation of discourse: the unity of work of architecture and urbanism. The spatial co-existence of different formal, technological and symbolic expressions would seem strange.

Well, much more contradictory would be to associate, at a conceptual and projective level, mani-

festations of the urban architecture with the Theory of Fractals, trying to identify in it a set of expressions that resulted from chaotic dynamic processes with visible occurrences of formal, functional and structural self-similarities, of typological repetitions in different contexts and scales. (Mandelbrot, 1983). In the same direction the set of concepts and notions developed by Gilles Deleuze, which contributes to the reading of the "movement", is considered of difficult assimilation, for example the different/repetitive, possible/real, virtual/real conceptual pairs, and especially the concept of rhizome elaborated together with Félix Guattari.

Other thinkers elaborated notions and concepts that can contribute to the referred rereading, in a very variable form, as in the case of Jacques Derrida who tried to subdue the classical logical form adopting the deconstruction concept, or the concept of hyperspace elaborated by Frederic Jameson, equivalent to Marc Augé's non-places, fostered by disorientation and non spatial identification of determined typological organizations of urban architecture. We could still refer to the transaesthetic notion elaborated by Baudrillard, taking into account the viral proliferation of elements and architectonic typologies, and consequently, an informational explosion, a trivial process that endows no references to the aesthetic evaluation, apart from any connotation of value. Moreover, the use of the literary image, the labyrinth, recreated by Borges can contribute to the proposed rereading, as well as the concept of technological/space/time mentioned earlier.

During the 1st DOCOMOMO "(Re)-discussing the modern" we presented a brief text "The heterotopia of the modern"(Cardoso, Oliveira, 1997: pp. 214-220), making some considerations on a building in Salvador, which was the pioneer of modern architecture in Bahia/Salvador/Brasil, using as its rereading Foucault's notion of heterotopia.

Considering the limitations imposed by the organizers of the event in terms of the length of the text, we will try to further develop one of the concepts we consider vital for the Theory and History of Urban Architecture in the new formation of discourse. We chose the concept of rhizome developed by Deleuze Guattari, in one of the most significant texts of the contemporaneous reading: "A Thousand Plateaus". It is an "ontology" of physics, logic, psychology, moral, politics".

According to the mentioned authors:

A rhizome has neither beginning nor end but always a middle (milieu), between things, inter-being, intermezzo. The tree is an affiliation, but the rhizome is the alliance, a sole alliance. The tree imposes the verb "to be" but the cloth of the rhizome

is the conjunction 'and... and.. and...!. This conjunction is strong enough to shake up and uproot the verb to be. It does not designate a correlation that can be located, going from one to another and vice-versa, but a perpendicular direction, a transversal movement that carries one and the other, a stream that has neither beginning nor end, eroding both banks and acquiring speed in the middle" (Deleuze, Guattari, 1996:37).

To the authors, this concept means that multiplicity form the own reality, they do not suppose a unit, do not go into totality or send to a subject. And they add: "the characteristic principles of multiplicity relate to the elements that are singularities: their relationships becomings; the events haecceities (individuation without subject) their spaces-time free spaces and times; the model of realization that is the rhizome (in opposition to the model of the tree); and its composition plan, forming plateaus, (zones of continuous intensity) vectors that cross them and form territories and grades of deterritorialization (idem: 8) (Our emphasis).

With the emergence of this new concept, Foucault's heterotopia concept acquires a new dimension, because at this moment we are facing "all kinds of coexistent formations". Quoting the authors mentioned above, it is possible to announce that in an urban architecture "as in anything else, there are lines of articulation or segmentarity, strata, territories, but also lines of escape, deterritorialization and desestratification movements. According to these lines, the compared velocities of drainage create the relative phenomenon of delay, of viscosity or on the contrary, of precipitation and rupture".

This set of attributions, transferred to urban architecture as lines and velocity of production and expression is a "negotiation". Multiplicity is not easy to be understood and adopted. The binary logic, the biunique relationships and the idea of unity still dominate the ways of thinking inherited from modernity. The attempts to break the linear unit of knowledge, as they send to the cyclic unit of the "everlasting return", or even the admission of multifaceted systems, present no true rupture with dualism, with the complementarity of a subject and an object, of a natural and spiritual reality. The unity, although denied and hindered in the object, makes it triumph, using a new kind of unit. In the subject. In a rhizome, affirm the referred authors: "on the contrary, each trace does not necessarily send to a new linguistic trace; all sorts of semiotic chains are connected to a very diverse way of condensing: biologic chains, policies, economies, bringing into play not only different systems of signs, but also statutes of states of things".

The conclusion reached is that a rhizome would not stop connecting the semiotic chains, the orga-

nizations of power, events related to the arts and social fights. In the cities, the repertoire of semiotic chains at different levels (formal, functional and structural) comprise diversified nature occurrences: of linguistics, perspectives, mimics, gestures; cognitive ones. This is equivalent to saying that there is no isolated language, nor universality of language, but a coexistence of dialects, patois, slang, and special languages. This is a very heterogeneous reality (heterotopic coexistence). There is no matrix of language, but the uptake of power for a hegemonic language inserted into a political multiplicity.

In sum, the concept of rhizome presupposes principles of connection, heterogeneity and rupture. It cannot be understood by any structural or generative model (system, organism). It is strange to any idea of the genetic axis or profound structure. It does not present the logic of the tree (of transference and reproduction). The rhizome can be considered an antigeology. "It is a short memory or an antimemory".

Different from Virilio, Deleuze and Guattari end up privileging the space instead of time. Everything is coextensive to everything and they conceive ontology as geology: instead of the being, the earth with its physical-chemical, organic, anthropomorphic strata. There is no opposition between man and nature, but symbiosis and alliance. "There is only becoming, no negation or deprivation. Becoming is always positive and amidst the positive ones, some are lost, blocked, dead. It is a very difficult task for a theorist and historian of the city to adopt the concept of rhizome in its integrity, considering that a rhizome has neither a beginning nor end but always a middle, a milieu. It is and inter-being, intermezzo. Therefore, the authors go on commenting that:

"The tree imposes the verb "to be", but the cloth of the rhizome is the conjunction 'and... and... and...!. This conjunction is strong enough to shake and uproot the verb to be. To do tabula rasa, start or restart from zero, searching a new beginning, or a fundament imply on a false conception of the trip and of the movement (methodic, pedagogic, iniciatic, symbolic). Kleist, Lenz or Buchner have another way of traveling and also of moving, from the middle, by the middle, getting in and out, without beginning or ending". (idem: 37) (Our emphasis).

The repertoire of notions and concepts applied to the theory and history of urban architecture is very vast. Regarding the modern period, there is a set of key words that form the basis for the formation of discourse. Besides the notions and concepts mentioned earlier (unity, continuity, etc) it is worth

reminding those emerging constantly in discourse: rationalism, form, function, structure, organism (organic architecture), expressionism, constructivism, beside a set of aesthetics/gestalt attributions, balance, order, movement, rhythm, transparency, lightness, pregnancy, amongst others, expressing some indicators of process projects. However little do they tell us about semiotic and cultural chains, etc., connected to very different ways of codification, bringing into play not only different regimes of sign in the domain of heterogeneity and ruptures.

Finally, it is worth emphasizing that the adoption of the concept of rhizome must be understood in the sense of overcoming the binary and dialectic way of thinking. However, it is obvious that this form will not disappear, but it will gradually lose its hegemonic feature in discourse and in the modalities of conception of the world. It then assumes an instrumental role, especially regarding the performance of discourse, in the connections and articulations called by Virilio "the aesthetics of apparition", of perception, opposing to the "aesthetics of disappearance, of the "a-perception", of the "trans-appearance" promoted by the new technologies.

We would like to approach other emerging notions and concepts in the new contemporaneous formation of discourse, however, we will only make brief references to them, leaving their details for another opportunity. However, we acknowledge their pertinence in the new modern architecture discourse. Amongst them, there is the notion of "deconstruction" in architecture, inspired in Jacques Derrida's critical texts to the classical ontology and implemented by the architect Peter Eisenman. The latter developed this notion, giving it a practical/theoretical support, in the sense of reinforcing the negativity of composition classical notions, centrality and continuity thought an incursion in the topological geometry, in an attempt to overcome the Euclidean geometry. Regardless of the theoretical tone of Eisenman's discourse, it is a question of contradictory nihilist positivism, in showing the presence of the absence, or in other words, "the pleasures of the absence". However, in our understanding, the attempt of deconstructing the Euclidean geometry did not take place. It is an ontological radicalization (not being) in the time/space context inherited from tradition, even though this new rational enabled the forging of a contemporaneous trend in architecture called "deconstructivism".

Theorists and disseminators of this new trend recognize that this posture of rupture with the classical paradigms of physical space organization found also repercussion in the pioneer proposals of the "Russian constructivism", considering this modern architecture movement a precursor of the present trend

(Papadakis, 1989: 11). It is very true that regarding the Russian constructivism the terminology is still confusing, thus creating difficulties for the scholars to have a bibliographic systematization on the subject. This results from the own notion that oscillates between the ideal of attending and satisfying the needs of a future society without classes (socialism construction), together with the intention of dominating the technology available at that time (of steel, of the engine) and in the strict sense, of Western inspiration, attributed to the revolution in Fine Arts, that took place before the Russian revolution, with objectives totally disassociated from utilitarian content or social commitment (Lodder, 1988: 5).

If we compare Boccioni's "development of a bottle" (1912) and Tatlin's model of "Monument to the Third International" (1920) it is then possible to establish between the two proposals a profound intention of subverting conventional references of the time/space relationship. Still very elementary deconstruction regarding the logical rigor of someone like Eisenman. The analogies established between "The City of El Lissitzky" (1921) and Tschumi's "La Vilette" (19984) or Lissitzky's "Proun SA" (1921) and Hadid's "Trafalgar Square" (1985); Stenberg's and Chernikhov's metal constructions (1921) with "La Vilette", present in the Catherine's Cooke accurate study, induce us to suppose that amidst ideological and Utopian presuppositions and of the socialism construction, there are strong indications of deconstructivism postures of the usual Euclidean's matrix of physical space (item: 21 to 64). The referred author expands her perception, including in this deconstruction intention the Russian theorists' ideas about the city: the "de-urbanization" (1929). Cooke dares to make an unusual parallel between the rhythm of the distribution of settlement ranges in the territorial level of the proposals of the Russians de-urbanists and the cinematic sequence of elements from "La Vilette", trying to establish conceptual coexistence, a kind of fractal view of the auto-similarity, in different contexts and scales.

We could go on with the hyperspace notion that will probably also find shelter in the modern architecture discourse. A notion developed by Jameson and that is equivalent to the connotation of "no place". A notion related with the dearth of orientation and identification in the physical space, and also, dependent on the way displacement provokes sensations of discomfort, vertigo, in the presence of configurations and complex architectonic typologies, in the form of a labyrinth, simulations, velocities, etc. The hyperspace is related with schemes of perception that extrapolate the usual perception, developing the sensorial capacity in experiences that no one had thought of. (Jameson, 1989: 74).

Today, the sophisticated airports, theme parks, shopping malls, the lexicon and syntax found in Las Vegas configure hyperspaces, no-places. In a certain way, this disorientation and spatial non-identification could be found in a set of modern architecture and urbanism proposals, both in the proposals of the Russian constructivists as well as in the Western Hemisphere, in Mario Chiatttoni's drawings in his "Metropolis" (1914) and especially in Saint'Elia's proposals of "La Città Nuova" and "Station for Airports and Trains" (1914), in which the futurist set of ideas enables a disturbing spatiality regarding the traditional schemes of perceiving architecture and the city.

I will only mention one more notion that may have a strong repercussion in the theory and historiography of architecture, the notion of technological/space/time". Since Bergson's philosophical speculations, simultaneous to the advent of the Theory of Relativity, the variable time (becoming) has assumed a hegemonic position in discourse regarding space (be). To produce speed became an obsession of modernity, promoting a kind of "shrinking of space effect". With the advent of the train, steam, telephone, airplane and the radio speed played an outstanding role in the urbanization processes. The equation "time is money" became the dilemma of the capitalist system throughout its different phases. The development of modernity technology/mechanics played a premonition role in the search of the instantaneity of the present as a simulation of the future. Both the duration of Bergson's "instant" in philosophy, as well as the futurist movement performance, whose premise of time is speed, can be interpreted as "a frozen" perceptive instant. A metaphor, or in other words, a condensation of time: "the permanent present", a premonition of the technological/space/time. The mechanical speed of modernity, the Bergsonian "instant" and its adoption by the futurists, must also be interpreted as a process of erasing reality from the present facts and things, configured in the "real time" advent of the electronic technologies. In the scope of this question, Virilio asks:

According to Gaborian, if time is one more obscurity that erases the material traces one by one, separating them from the reality of facts and things, what can we say about the effect of the time-light reality, of a false proximity of a world without thickness and shade, whose promised unification enchanted McLuhan?"

Before concluding, we find appropriate to establish a relationship between the state of the art of theory and history of architecture and the new electronic technologies that are progressively abolishing the notions of physical dimension, since we are witnessing a transmutation of the representations. It is possible to confirm that:

"To the emergence of forms and volumes appropriate to persist in the duration of their material support, there is a succession of images whose sole duration is the persistence in the retina... if yesterday the architectonic could be compared to geology, to the tectonic of the natural projections, to the pyramids, to the neo-gothic sinuosity, from now on it can only be compared to the leading edge technologies, whose vertiginous deeds exile us from the horizon of the earth" (Virilio, 1995; 1921).

Conclusions

In this new cultural/technological context that enables inexhaustible informational files, having in mind the Internet and the other communications means (TV, VIDEO, CD-ROM, etc.), our question is: how can we use the potentialities of the new cyberspace technologies focusing on the professional formation of the architect regarding the disciplines of the theory and history of architecture, and in this specific case, of modern architecture? The presupposition is that as a generator of cyberculture, the Internet together with the vast repertoire of images, can offer conceptual texts pertinent to the new contemporaneous formation of discourse about architecture and its history. In case this does not happen, we will be facing the most rigorous academic repetition. According to Deleuze, repetition occurs when we refer to "elements that are really distinct; however they have strictly the same concept. The repetition appears, then, as a difference without concept". (Deleuze, 1988: pp. 19-43).

Thus, the responsibility of the "virtual communities" that deal with the theory and history of architecture go beyond the traditional academia classroom environments, assuming a dimension and a range never thought of before for the formation of the 21st century architect. It is true that this rereading proposal is still incipient, however it seems to promise a stimulating route. There are many difficulties. It is not easy for an architect theorist and historian to absorb and adopt the concept of rhizome in the theory and history of architecture. It is understandable that it is not an established practice in the architecture academia, "to start from the middle, by the middle, entering and leaving, with neither a beginning nor an end" and least of all "to produce the unconscious and based on it a new enunciation, giving credit to Deleuze's motto "make a rhizome and not a root, never plant! Do not sow, pick up. Do not be one or the other, be multiplicities" (Deleuze, Guattari, 1936: 28,36).

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Baudrillard, Jean. (1990). *A Transparência do Mal*. Campinas: Papyrus.

- Benjamin, Andrew. (1989). *Deconstrucion*. N.Y.: Rizzoli.
- Deleuze, Gilles. Guattari, Felix. (1996). *Mil Platôs*. Rio de Janeiro: Ed.34, vol.1. Deleuze, Gilles. (1988). *Diferença e Repetição*. São Paulo: Graal.
- Foucault, Michel. (1987). *Arqueologia do Saber*. Rio de Janeiro: Forense.Universitário.
- Grau, Cristina. (1995). *Borges y la arquitectura*. Madrid: Catedra.
- Heisenberg, Werner. (1995). *Física e Filosofia*. Brasília: ed. UnB.
- Jameson, Fredric. (1989). *Il Post Moderno - o La Logica del Tardo Capitalismo*. Milão: Garzanti.
- Jencks, Charles. (1989). *Arquitetura Internacional - Últimas tendências*. Barcelona: Gili.
- Lodder, Christina. (1988). *El Construtivismo Russo*. Madrid: Alianza Forma.
- Mandelbrot, Benoit. (1983). *The Fractal Geometry of Nature*. N.Y.: Freeman.
- Meyer, Ester da Costa. (1995). *The work of Antonio Sant'Elia*. Yale: Yale University.
- Puppi, Marcelo. (1998). *Por uma História não moderna da Arquitetura Brasileira*. Campinas: Pontes/CPHA/IFCH.
- Rossi, Aldo. (1980). *L'architettura della città*. Pádua: Ed. Marsilio. 2a. ed.
- Tafuri, Manfredo. (1972). *La Sfera e il Labirinto*. Turim: Einaudi.
- Venturi, Robert. (1977). *Complejidad y Contradiccion en la arquitectura*. Barcelona: Gili.
- Venturi, Robert. Scott, Brown Denise. Izenour, Steven. (1995). *Learning from Las Vegas*. Cambridge: MIT Press.
- Virilio, Paul. (1969). *O espaço crítico ("The critical space")*. Rio de Janeiro: ed. 34.
- Virilio, Paul. (1995). *A arte do Motor*. São Paulo: Ed. Liberdade.
- Zevi, Bruno. (1961). *Architettura in nuce*. Madrid: Aguilar.

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